

NOTES

Stability Constants of Dioxouranium(VI), Th(IV), Ce(III) and In(III) Complexes with 7-Nitroso-8-Quinolinol-5-Sulphonic Acid

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SINCE, 7-nitroso-8-hydroxyquinolene-5-sulphonic acid is a very interesting reagent in chemical analysis¹⁻⁵, the determination of the stability constants of metal complexes seems to be quite important. This prompted us to extend the technique for determining the stepwise proton-reagents constant of this ligand and its chelate stability constants with $UO_2(II)$, Th(IV), Ce(III) and In(III).

Experimental

Materials and Solutions :

7-Nitroso-8-quinolinol-5-sulphonic acid was prepared according to Lee⁶, and its purity was checked by elemental analysis. Stock solution ($10^{-2}M$) of the ligand was prepared in doubly distilled water. $10^{-2}M$ solutions of metal ions were prepared by dissolving the AnalaR B.D.H. nitrates of $UO_2(II)$, Th(IV) and Ce(III) and the AnalaR B.D.H. Chloride of In(III) in doubly distilled water and standardized by conventional gravimetric procedures. NaOH (B.D.H.), $NaClO_4$ (c.p., Riedel) and $HClO_4$ (E. Merck) solutions were prepared in CO_2 -free doubly distilled water. NaOH and $HClO_4$ solutions were standardized by known method.

The pH-titrations were carried out in CO_2 -free nitrogen at $30 \pm 1^\circ$ with a PHM 64, Research pH-meter accurate to ± 0.005 unit with glass-calomel electrode assembly and calibrated against standard buffers.

Titration procedure :

The experimental method of Bjerrum and Calvin as modified by Irving and Rossotti⁷ was used to determine \bar{n} and pL values. The following carbonate-free solutions (total volume 25 ml, ionic strength adjusted to 0.1M, $NaClO_4$) were titrated potentiometrically with NaOH : (A) 2.5 ml $HClO_4$ (0.025 M) ; (B) mixture A containing 0.0005M

ligand ; (C) mixture B containing 0.0005M metal ion solution ; (D) mixture B containing 0.00025M metal ion solution. pH values were plotted against the volumes of alkali added (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. pH-titration curves ; A : $HClO_4$ (0.0025M) ; B : ligand (0.0005M) ; C : Ce(III) (0.00025M) ; D : In(III) (0.00025M) ; E : $UO_2(II)$ (0.00025M) ; F : Th(IV) (0.00025M). $C_{NaOH} = 0.0051M$ except E = 0.0056M.

Results and Discussion

Proton-ligand formation constants :

From the titration curves of solutions (A) and (B) of acid alone and in the presence of ligand, the proton-ligand formation number \bar{n}_A was calculated at various pH values and plotted against pH to get the proton-ligand formation curve (Fig. 2), from which the proton-ligand formation constants were evaluated by the method of Irving and Rossotti⁷. These were found to amount to $pK_{(NH)} = 4.82$ and $pK_{(OH)} = 8.41$. These values correspond to the

Fig. 2. Proton-ligand formation curve.

following neutralization reaction :

Metal-ligand stability constants :

Fig. 1 reveals that the metal ligand titration curves are well separated from the ligand titration curve indicating the liberation of proton through complex formation between the ligand and the metal ions under investigation.

The average number of ligand molecules attached per metal ion (\bar{n}) and the free ligand exponent pL were calculated at different pH 's by Irving and Rossotti technique using the titration curves of solutions (B), (C) and (D) and the values of pK_a for the ligand. The formation curves for the different complexes were plotted from the \bar{n} and pL values (Fig. 3). However, \bar{n} values greater than 2, have not been obtained in any cases. It is, therefore, concluded that only 1 : 1 and 1 : 2 (metal-ligand) complexes are possible to be formed in each system.

The formation curves were analysed to get $\log \beta_1$ and $\log \beta_2$ for the different complexes by correction term method⁷. Furthermore the \bar{n} , pL data were utilised for evaluating $\log \beta$ by the method adopted by Hearson and Gillbert⁸ and that adopted by Martell *et al*⁹. These methods are taken in Table 1, as (a), (b) and (c) respectively. The stability constant values obtained from these computational techniques are summarized in Table 1.

Fig. 3. Formation curves of 7-nitroso-8-quinolinol-5-sulphonic acid complexes with: Ce(III); $UO_2(II)$; In(III) and Th(IV).TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS OF METAL COMPLEXES OF 7-NITROSO-8-QUINOLINOL-5-SULPHONIC ACID AT $30 \pm 1^\circ$ ($\mu = 0.1M NaClO_4$)

	Computational method	$UO_2(II)$	Th(IV)	Ce(III)	In(III)
Log β_1	(a)	3.98	5.48	3.81	4.98
	(b)	3.95	5.42	3.80	5.00
	(c)	4.00	5.48	3.78	4.95
Log β_2	(a)	8.24	9.98	8.15	9.52
	(b)	8.22	9.92	8.20	9.56
	(c)	8.21	9.96	8.12	9.54

The results listed in this table indicate that the stability of the different complexes investigated follow the order :

The lower stability of the Ce(III) complex relative to the other metal complexes can be ascribed to the fact that the lanthanide complexes are substantially dissociated in aqueous solutions¹⁰. On the other hand, the higher stability of Th(IV) complexes relative to In(III) and $UO_2(II)$ complexes is due to the high positive charge on Th(IV) which makes it much susceptible to complex formation than In(III) and $UO_2(II)$.

References

- D. H. LEE, *Daehan Hwahak Hwoeje*, 1965, 9, 101.
- M. A. EL-DAWY, A. S. TAWFIK and S. R. ELSHABOURI, *J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1976, 65, 644.
- M. M. ALY and FRESNIUS, *Z. Anal. Chem.*, 1974, 270, 32.
- S. A. ABBASI, B. G. BHAT and R. S. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1976, 14(A), 215.
- S. A. ABBASI, B. G. BHAT and R. S. SINGH, *Anal. Chem.*, 1976, 282, 222.

6. D. H. LEE, *Daehan Hwahak Hwojee*, 1965, 9, 37.
7. H. M. IRVING and H. S. ROSSOTTI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1954, 2904.
8. J. Z. HEARSON and J. B. GILLBERT *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1955, 77, 2594.
9. C. F. RICHARD, R. L. GUSTAFSON and A. E. MARTELL, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1959, 81, 1033.
10. S. A. COTTON and F. A. HART, *The heavy transition elements*, (Macmillan Press Ltd. London), 1975, p. 206.

New Iron(III) Complexes with Dibasic Tridentate ONO Donor Schiff Bases Derived from Salicylaldehyde, Substituted Salicylaldehyde and Alcoholamines

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In recent years the magnetic exchange interactions in transition metal complexes have been the subject of many investigations¹⁻⁵. These studies have mostly veered around $S = \frac{1}{2}$ systems and far fewer studies have been reported on $S = 1, 2, 3/2$ and $5/2$ systems. The iron(III) complexes ($S = 5/2$ system) of Schiff bases serve as models for biologically important compounds like haemerythrin and haem protein systems. Although in copper(II) and oxovanadium(IV) complexes of I, the magnetic properties of the complexes are quite different in $n = 2$ and 3 complexes⁶⁻⁷, such difference has not been observed in the iron(III) complexes^{8,9}. The substitution of hydrogen atoms in methylene linkage in I may influence the magnetic properties of iron(III) complexes of I and no such study has so far been reported. In order to know the effect of substitution in the methylene linkage and also on the effect of size of the chelate ring on the magnetic properties of iron(III) complexes we have synthesized several new iron(III) complexes of tridentate dibasic Schiff bases(II) and (III). A comparison of magnetic properties of iron(III) complexes of the ligands (I-III) is presented.

I. $n = 2, 3$

Experimental

Salicylaldehyde and ethanolamine were of BDH reagent grade. 2-Hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde and isopropanolamine were the products of Fluka AG, Switzerland. 2-Amino-2-methylpropanol was purchased from Koch-Light Lab., England. Propanolamine was obtained from Aldrich Chemical Co., U. S. A. Anhydrous ferric chloride was obtained from BDH.

Iron was determined by potassium dichromate¹⁰ after decomposing the complex with concentrated nitric acid and then igniting to Fe_2O_3 . Chlorine was determined gravimetrically as AgCl after fusing the complex in a nickel crucible with sodium peroxide and sodium hydroxide mixture. The elemental analyses were done by the microanalytical services of the University of Bombay. Infrared spectra were recorded in nujol mulls on Beckman IR 20 and Perkin-Elmer 620 infrared spectrophotometers. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out by a Gouy balance using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as the calibrant. The diamagnetic corrections were calculated by using Pascal's constants. The conductance measurements were carried out in tetrahydrofuran solution (0.001M) using Toshniwal type CLO-C₂A conductivity bridge and a dip type cell. The molecular weight measurements were carried out by the Rast method¹¹ using diphenyl as the solvent. We have noticed that diphenyl is a better solvent in comparison to camphor in terms of reproducibility, and the molal boiling point elevation constant of diphenyl was found to be 6.8.

General method of preparation of the complexes :

Salicylaldehyde or 2-hydroxy-1-naphthaldehyde (0.02 mol) was condensed with the equimolar amount of the appropriate alkanolamine by refluxing in 30-60 ml absolute alcohol for 30 mins to give the yellow Schiff base solution. Anhydrous ferric chloride (3.24 g, 0.02 mol) was dissolved in 30 ml of absolute alcohol. To this the Schiff base solution was added and the mixture was refluxed for 2 hr. The separated reddish brown precipitates were suction filtered, washed with absolute alcohol and dried *in vacuo* at room temperature. Yield = 15%.

Results and Discussion

The analytical data for complexes (Table I) indicate that the metal : ligand ratio is 1 : 1. The electrolytic conductance measurements in tetrahydrofuran show that the complexes are non-electrolytes ($\Lambda_M = 8 - 13 \text{ ohm}^{-1} \text{ cm}^2 \text{ mole}^{-1}$). The ir spectra of the complexes do not exhibit any $\nu(\text{O}-\text{H})$ band. This shows that there is no water molecule present in the complexes and both the replaceable hydrogen atoms of the ligands are